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INCLUSION: PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE AND THE VARIOUS

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ABSTRACT

Pedagogical Practice is understood as a complex social practice that takes place in different spaces/times of the school, especially in the classroom, mediated by the teacher-student-knowledge interaction. When theory and practice are articulated, human activity is reflected in the transformation of the human being and society itself. In line with what has been reflected, the school needs to have a plural positioning, be a humane place of welcome, and bring a policy of overcoming exclusion. In the words of Arroyo (2013), “the unequal”, the “others” and the “diverse” (blacks, indigenous people, quilombolas, rural people, people on the margins of poverty, different cultures, races, religions, gender issues, social conditions, physical and neurological disabilities) are arriving at school, marked by social inequality, and the school must treat everyone equally.